

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Breeding methods—hybrid

Performance of IR rice hybrids in Ambasamudram, Tamil Nadu, India

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We evaluated rice hybrids IR54752A/IR46R, IR54752A/IR54R, and IR54752A/ARC11353R, with IR20 and Co 43 as local checks. Twenty-day-old seedlings were transplanted 26 Jun 1988 and harvested the last week of Oct. Plots were 3 × 1.2 m with a 15- × 10-cm spacing between plants, in a randomized block design, with two replications.

Yields were assessed on whole plots; biometrical observations were taken on 10 plants/replication. Entries also were screened for reaction to major pests and diseases.

Only IR54752A/IR46 yielded higher than the checks, although the differ-

ence from Co 43 was not significant (Table 1). IR54752A/IR46 matured 5 d earlier, had more productive tillers and higher panicle weight than the checks.

All three hybrids were resistant to stem borer, gall fly, brown planthopper, and sheath blight, and moderately resistant to grain discoloration (Table 2). □

Table 2. Reaction of IRRI rice hybrids to major pests and diseases in the field at RRS, Ambasamudram, Tamil Nadu, India, 1988.

Hybrid or check	Reaction ^a				
	Insects			Diseases	
	Stem borer	Gall fly	Brown planthopper	Sheath blight	Grain discoloration
IR54752A/IR46	1	1	-	3	5
IR54752A/IR54	1	1	-	3	5
IR54752A/ARC11353	1	1	-	3	5
IR20	3	1	5	3	3
Co 43	5	1	3	3	3

^aStandard evaluation system for rice scale.

Table 1. Performance of IRRI rice hybrids at RRS, Ambasamudram, Tamil Nadu, India, 1988.

Hybrid or check	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Productive tillers (no.)	Unproductive tillers (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle weight (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase over IR20 (%)	Increase over Co 48 (%)
IR54752A/IR46	130	105.2	11.1	1.1	24.5	35.3	5.5	19.5	14.6
IR54752A/IR54	135	95.8	10.1	1.9	26.0	29.3	4.7	2.1	-
IR54752A/ARC11353	135	89.4	9.5	2.5	25.0	32.9	4.7	2.1	-
IR20	133	88.1	8.0	1.5	24.9	28.9	4.6	-	-
Co 43	139	82.3	8.5	2.5	25.0	29.0	4.8	4.3	-
LSD							0.9		
CV (%)							9.4		

Ease of fertility restoration in CMS lines

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We evaluated 36 experimental rice hybrids involving cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines V20A, IR46830A, and IR48483A and 12 restorer lines and their male parents during 1987 wet season. Each line was grown in one row of 12 plants at 20- × 20-cm spacing, in a randomized complete block design

with three replications. Check varieties were PR103 (125 d duration) and PR106 (144 d). Data on grain yield and percent spikelet fertility were collected from the center 10 plants of each row.

None of the hybrids outyielded PR106 (see table). Most of them had short duration. When compared with short-duration check PR103, hybrid combinations V20A/PR103 (120 d) and V20A/PAU50-B-25-1-5 (128 d) had significantly higher yields. This indicates that the performance of hybrids should be compared with checks of similar duration.

The CMS lines used have the same (WA) source of cytoplasm imparting male sterility. But they exhibited different fertility restoration with different restorer lines. PAU50-B-25-1-5 was a good restorer for V20A (82.53% fertile spikelets), but a poor restorer for IR46830A and IR48483A (59.93 and 41.82% spikelet fertility, respectively). Responses with other restorer lines were similar. Hybrids with CMS line V20A uniformly exhibited high grain yield and percent filled spikelets, indicating that V20A was the easiest line to restore. □

Yield, spikelet fertility, and days to maturity of hybrids using 12 restorer lines.^a Punjab, India.

Male parent	Grain yield (g)/10 plants			Male parent selfed	Spikelet fertility (%)			Male parent selfed	Days to maturity			Male parent	
	Hybrid combination with				Hybrid combination with				Hybrid combination with				
	V20A	IR46830A	IR48483A		V20A	IR46830A	IR48483A		V20A	IR46830A	IR48483A		
PAU50-B-25-1-5	420.33	138.67	102.00	280.00	82.53	59.93	41.82	88.85	128	130	138	143	
PAU158-68-1-1	340.00	123.67	72.67	229.00	83.96	60.94	43.63	88.26	123	123	123	133	
PAU164-11-3-4-1	334.67	309.33	268.33	259.00	78.15	76.69	75.93	87.12	140	133	138	141	
IR18341-37-3-2	324.67	148.00	111.33	247.00	91.35	75.15	57.65	84.48	135	138	138	138	
IR21820-154-3-2-2-2-3	296.00	195.67	158.00	235.67	80.47	68.89	49.24	85.74	138	136	137	140	
IR28178-82-31	334.33	209.67	166.00	222.67	83.02	72.15	60.77	89.01	133	126	129	138	
MRC603-3-3	366.67	85.33	45.33	226.33	79.26	60.63	34.48	80.05	126	124	121	123	
BR51-282-7	278.33	155.67	128.67	271.33	85.55	73.21	75.29	87.21	128	126	126	141	
UPR82-1-1	367.33	135.33	94.67	248.00	87.59	71.95	65.93	87.88	118	122	120	115	
Palman 579	194.00	76.67	52.00	229.00	72.25	46.66	34.32	89.15	123	128	128	126	
PR103	427.67	300.33	255.33	368.33	83.20	75.60	72.39	88.46	120	123	122	125	
PR106	328.00	245.33	155.00	416.67	82.66	72.64	52.08	84.96	128	132	131	144	
LSD													
		Grain yield		Spikelet fertility									
		0.05-13.078		0.05-1.115									
		0.01-17.142		0.01-2.866									

^aPR106 = best check.

Effect of cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS) on panicle exertion and sheath rot (ShR) incidence in F₂ rice hybrids

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We studied the F₂ progenies of indica rice hybrids Zhen Shan 97A/IR50, Er-jiu-nan 1A/IR50, and MS37A/IR50 carrying wild abortive CMS in 1988 wet season. Segregants were examined for pollen and spikelet fertility, panicle exertion, and ShR incidence.

All crosses segregated for fertile, partially fertile, and sterile classes on the basis of pollen and spikelet fertility (see table). Panicle exertion was invariably poor in all the sterile and

near sterile plants in all crosses. All plants with well-exserted or moderately well-exserted panicles were completely fertile.

ShR incidence was severe in plants with poorly exerted panicles. The higher ShR incidence in sterile plants

was attributed to half-opened leaf sheaths covering the lower half of the panicles: that favored infection.

We conclude that panicle exertion might be under the influence of cytoplasmic-genetic factors that control CMS in rice. □

Effect of CMS on panicle exertion, fertility, and ShR incidence in the F₂ of hybrid rices. Madurai, India, 1988.

Hybrid	Panicle exertion	Spikelet fertility (%)	Pollen fertility (%)	ShR incidence ^a
Zhen Shan 97A/IR50	Partly exerted	0.0 - 33.7	0.0 - 30.0	7
	Just exerted	40.3 - 96.8	30.0 - 100.0	5
	Moderately well- or well-exserted	>90.0	90.0 - 100.0	1
Er-jiu-nan 1A/IR50	Partly exerted	0.0 - 28.2	0.0 - 30.0	7
	Just exerted	41.0 - 98.3	30.0 - 100.0	3
	Moderately well- or well-exserted	>90.0	90.0 - 100.0	1
MS37A/IR50	Partly exerted	0.0 - 43.8	0.0 - 30.0	7-9
	Just exerted	60.1 - 100.0	30.0 - 100.0	5
	Moderately well- or well-exserted	>90.0	90.0 - 100.0	1

^aStandard evaluation system for rice scale.

Identification of restorers and maintainers for male sterile lines at CLRRI

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We testcrossed 22 short- and medium-duration rice cultivars with cytoplasmic male sterile lines IR46829A, IR46830A, IR48483A, and IR54752A, than 10% fertility as suspected maintainers.

OM576, OM80, IR66, and IR29723-143-3-2-2-2-1 were identified as

effective restorers for IR46830A and IR54752A (see table). OM86-9, OM90, and IR31868-64-2-3-3-3 were effective restorers for IR48483A. to identify fertility restorers and sterility maintainers.

Hybrids and their male parents were transplanted in 1987-88 dry and wet